

Electromagnetic Design of an Inductive Wireless Power Transfer System for Endoscopic Capsule

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Abstract

The power and energy demand for the instrumentation implemented in endoscopy capsules is such that a power supply from electrochemical cells is inappropriate. In this paper the electromagnetic design of the Wireless Power Transfer (WPT) system of the autonomous multimodal implantable endoscopic capsule designed within the project AUTOCAPSULE is firstly described. In particular, the design of the inductive link between the transmitting and the receiving coils is presented by showing the main involved parameters. The choice of wire and number of turns for transmitting and receiving coils is discussed by taking into account the power transferred to the load and the design constraints on available space and tissue absorption. The problem of patient exposure to non-ionizing electromagnetic fields is treated with a 3-D FEM simulation. The WPT conceived system allows to satisfy the project requirements, i.e., a power transfer to the end-user of 150 mW at a distance up to 15 cm, showing as well compliance with SAR regulations.

Index Terms

Inductive Power Link, Implantable Device, Wireless Power Transfer, Wireless Capsule Endoscopy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of sensorized capsules is certainly a development from the methods popular to date to conduct endoscopy examinations [1]. A miniaturized capsule is able to perform in-depth examinations by possibly capturing images and acquiring data while minimizing invasiveness. Moreover, sections particularly difficult to reach with flexible cables, e.g. small intestine [2], can be investigated more easily. In order not to leave the capsule movement to chance, but instead control the investigation of specific portions of the gastrointestinal tract, several approaches were investigated in the literature to locate and maneuver the capsule. Solutions performing localization via magnetic field sensors [3], [4], Radio Frequency (RF) systems [5], microwave imaging [6], and gamma-ray-based solutions [7] have been proposed. Beside, capsule control can be obtained through magnetic-field systems [8], or locomotion apparatuses inside the capsule [9]–[11].

Of course, in the capsule electromagnetic design, a crucial point is the power supply requirement to manage motion control and data acquisition. Classical solutions foresaw the adoption of integrated electrochemical battery, as the system proposed by Carta *et al.* [12], able of 25 mW power supply for 6–8 hours. However, this is often inadequate and the only chance is the adoption of a Wireless Power Transfer (WPT) system [13]. The latter refers to a system that allows to transfer power from a source to a load without cable connections, by crossing a medium. Typically, a WPT system for capsule endoscopes operates in the near-field region by exploiting the inductive coupling between a transmitting (TX) coil connected to the source, and a receiving (RX) coil connected to the end-user system.

The design of both TX and RX coils has to satisfy some geometrical constraints, but the limit on the TX-coil design is typically less stringent, as expected. As an example, the TX coil can be a solenoid wrapped around the patient's torso [9], [14], [15], or a Helmholtz coil [16], [17]. The real sticking point is the RX coil layout, since it must share the volume within the capsule together with all other components, e.g. sensors, microprocessors. One of the main techniques for coil miniaturization is the adoption of a ferromagnetic core to concentrate the magnetic-field flux within the coil [9], [18], at the expense of bulk.

In addition to miniaturization, since the capsule orientation in the gastrointestinal tract is mostly random, the WPT for capsule endoscopy application must be guaranteed independently from capsule direction. The literature proposed both a realization of TX coils generating a 3-directions field [19], [20] and an implementation of 3-axis RX coils [21], [22]. The latter solution is

Fig. 1. Scheme of Wireless Power Transfer (WPT) in capsule endoscopy within the AUTOCAPSULE Project.

typically preferred [23] due to high inductive-link efficiency and no need of three external drives for power [20]. Moreover, the WPT system design has to comply with the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) regulation on human tissues.

The purpose of the AUTOCAPSULE system [24], a Horizon 2020 grant awarded project, is the development of an untethered endoscopic capsule, with the aim of providing a wireless autonomous system for early diagnosis and monitoring of gastrointestinal diseases. The AUTOCAPSULE ambitious vision is the miniaturization of several sub-systems inside the capsule, such as robotic automatic positioning, wireless power and data transfers, different multi-modal sensing systems, together with white light and micro ultrasound imaging. The typical usage of the AUTOCAPSULE system is depicted in Fig. 1, specifically focusing on capsule colonoscopy. Instead of using peristalsis to go through the gastrointestinal tract, with no control capability, an external robotic arm guides the capsule movement, and collected data are wirelessly transmitted from the capsule to an external unit. The capsule has no internal battery, but it is designed to be wirelessly powered from a transmitting coil. The latter is on a robotic arm and it is inductively linked to a 3-axis receiving coil within the capsule. To fulfill the design specifications, WPT should be granted for an overall consumption up to 150 mW at a distance of 15 cm.

In this paper, the electromagnetic design of the AUTOCAPSULE WPT system is firstly presented. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The circuit design is described in Section II with the main involved parameters. Section III illustrates the numerical model of both TX and RX coils by accounting for size constraints, power transfer efficiency and tissue absorption. Then, a preliminary measurement setup is presented. Finally, Section IV draws some conclusions and outlines future work.

II. CIRCUIT MODEL

We conducted the design of TX and RX coils by implementing resonant circuits [25]. We adopted the lumped-parameter model for the equivalent circuit of TX and RX coils of the WPT system (Fig. 2). To implement a resonant system, the inductive behavior of the coil has to be compensated through the use of a capacitor. The latter can be designed with a series connection or a parallel connection and its capacitance has to compensate the coil imaginary impedance at the operating frequency, f_0 . For the TX circuit we selected a series connection, while a parallel connection was chosen for the RX circuit. Such a configuration is the most suitable for voltage excitation at the source side and voltage rectification at the load side, as it is in our case [19].

Given the TX coil inductance, L_{TX} , and the power supply pulse, $\omega_0 = 2\pi f_0$, the capacitance required for the TX series resonance can be calculated as:

$$C_{TX} = \frac{1}{\omega_0^2 L_{TX}}, \quad (1)$$

while in the case of RX parallel resonance, the capacitance value can be calculated as:

$$C_{RX} = \frac{1}{2\omega_0^2 L_{RX}} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 - \frac{4\omega_0^2 L_{RX}^2}{R_L^2}} \right), \quad (2)$$

where L_{RX} is the RX coil inductance and R_L is the load impedance representing the final user system, namely voltage rectifier and capsule sensors. In the equivalent circuit, we considered also for the resistive behavior of coil wires through the terms R_{TX} and R_{RX} for TX and RX coils, respectively.

Fig. 2. Circuit model of the wireless power transfer system with a series-connection scheme for the transmitting coil and parallel one for the receiving coil.

Fig. 3. 2-D axisymmetric simulation geometry for TX and RX coils.

A. Power Transfer Efficiency

Coil performance is quantified through its quality factor Q , a dimensionless parameter which accounts for the amount of energy stored in the LC resonator and then dissipated on the resistor R . For the TX and RX coil, it is equal to:

$$Q_{TX} = \frac{\omega_0 L_{TX}}{R_{TX}}, \quad Q_{RX} = \frac{\omega_0 L_{RX}}{R_{RX}}, \quad (3)$$

respectively. In inductive WPT systems with TX coil directly connected to power source and RX coil directly connected to load, the maximum PTE, η_{max} , of the system can be written according to [26], [27], as:

$$\eta_{max} = \frac{\kappa^2 Q_{TX} Q_{RX}}{\left(1 + \sqrt{1 + \kappa^2 Q_{TX} Q_{RX}}\right)^2}, \quad (4)$$

where κ is the coupling coefficient, defined as $M/\sqrt{L_{TX}L_{RX}}$, being M the mutual impedance among coils. The product $\kappa^2 Q_{TX} Q_{RX}$ is also referred as the link potential X .

Instead, the effective efficiency, η , of the WPT link can be evaluated as in [27]:

$$\eta = \frac{X Q_{RX}}{(\omega_0 R_L C_{RX} + Q_{RX}) \left(\frac{Q_{RX}}{\omega_0 R_L C_{RX}} + X + 1 \right)}. \quad (5)$$

The value of quality factors, link potential, and the amount of power transferred to the load P_L , are used in the circuit of Fig. 2 to define the design of the two coils, presented in the following section.

III. COIL DESIGN

As already said, the AUTOCAPSULE system involved the adoption of a robotic arm to control and implement the endoscope capsule motion within the gastrointestinal tract. We chose the circular end-user of the above-mentioned robotic arm to install the WPT TX coil. This guarantees that TX and RX coils are almost centered each other along the whole path within the human body. The housing dimension for the TX coil limited its sizes to a radius of $r_{TX} = 9$ cm.

Fig. 4. Resistance (solid line) and Inductance (dashed line) as a function of number of coil windings for (a) TX and (b) RX. (c) Resulting quality factors for TX (solid line) and RX (dashed line) coils.

By concerning the RX coil, it had to fit a very small capsule with maximum sizes of a cube with 1-cm side. To guarantee appropriate performance independently on the capsule orientation with reference to the TX coil, we designed a 3-D coil. The latter consists on three equal coils with square section of 1-cm side, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Without loss of generality, only one of the three RX coils is considered in the follow to select the design parameter.

Due to the use of a magnet system for capsule motion-control through the robotic arm on patient body, no ferromagnetic cores can be used to intensify the linked magnetic flux, as often done in the open literature [9]. Thus, the RX coil was designed in free space.

The system working frequency was set to 6.78 MHz. This solution was a compromise between the efficiency of the energy transfer and the power absorption in the human tissues. Because of the selected resonance frequency, the coil wires consisted on enameled copper wires with a diameter of $d_{RX} = 0.05$ mm. In the TX coil, these were grouped to form a Litz wire consisting of 2000 strands with an equivalent diameter $d_{TX} = 2.8$ mm, while in the construction of RX coil only one strand was used. Indeed, the expected harmonic skin depth at 6.78 MHz for the copper is $\delta = \sqrt{\rho/\pi f \mu_0} \simeq 25$ μm , with $\rho = 1.68 \cdot 10^{-8} \Omega \cdot \text{m}$. In the RX coil, the enameled copper wire was wound with a spacing $s = 0.05$ mm among windings, so decreasing turn-to-turn capacitance and raise self-resonance frequency $f_s = 1/(2\pi\sqrt{L_{RX}C_p})$, with C_p being the parallel capacitance.

A. Numerical Simulations

To evaluate the coil parameters as a function of the number of turns N_{TX} and N_{RX} a 2-D axisymmetric FEM simulation was performed using the commercial software COMSOL Multiphysics®. The TX coil was simulated by imposing a uniform current distribution within it, to approximate the effects of Litz wire, then evaluating the internal resistance according to the guidance in DIN EN 60317-11. The RX coil was simulated as a single copper wire, and therefore skin effect and proximity effect were also considered. Coil section was considered as circular with radius $r_{RX} = 0.5$ cm, rather than squared, to exploit axial-symmetric simulations (Fig. 3). This notably reduces the computational cost, still accounting for electromagnetic-field diffusion within conductors. The parameters used in the simulation are listed in Fig. 3.

Fig. 4 shows first results of parameter simulation as a function of turn number. In both TX and RX coil cases, shown in Figs. 4 (a) and (b), respectively, resistance and inductance grow practically linearly with number of windings, albeit at different rates. This results in an increase of the quality factor with number of windings for both coils, with Q_{TX} ranging between 400 and 1200 for $2 < N_{TX} < 10$, and Q_{RX} ranging between 70 and 95 for $40 < N_{TX} < 90$ (Fig. 4 (c)). By considering space constraints imposed by the capsule as the main bond, we selected $N_{RX} = 90$ for the RX coil.

Fig. 5. Power transmitted to the load, P_L , as a function of the current on the TX coil I_{TX} for different distances between TX and RX coils: 10 cm (black solid line), 15 cm (black dashed line), and 20 cm (black dotted line).

TABLE I
TX AND RX COIL DESIGN PARAMETERS (FIG. 3).

Coil	N	r [cm]	wire type
TX	6	9	Litz - 2000×0.05 mm
RX	90	0.5	0.05 mm

Then, the inductive link was simulated for a distance between transmitter and receiver coils of 10 cm, 15 cm, and 20 cm. At a distance of 15 cm between the two coils, i.e. the system operating distance, the coupling factor κ is about 10^{-3} , leading to a link potential around 0.1 for $N_{TX} = 6$. Having a $X \ll 1$ leads to working under “low coupling” conditions [27], where the presence of the receiver does not affect the transmitter operation, although always working in near field. This allows for an independent optimization of the design of both coils. Fixed $N_{RX} = 90$, 6 windings for the TX coil were considered in the following as a compromise between a high quality factor (and thus efficiency), low currents needed to transmit power, and space requirements.

The power transmitted to the load, P_L , was evaluated by solving equations for the circuit in Fig. 2 as a function of the current on the TX coil I_{TX} , with Fig. 5 presenting the results.

The load resistance R_L is assumed to match the impedance seen at its terminal, thus realizing the condition of maximum power transfer. This will be possible through a dedicated rectifier integrated circuit, so implementing the condition of impedance conjugate matching, currently being developed within the project.

With the chosen coil parameters (Table I), the requirement of 150 mW (dashed red line in Fig. 5) is satisfied with a value of the current I_{TX} around 3.8 A at a distance of 15 cm (dashed black line in Fig. 5), for the operating frequency of 6.78 MHz. Such a current allows the transfer of about 43 mW at 20 cm distance, at the same frequency, while at shorter distances the coupling improves, with nearly 763 mW transferred at 10 cm. At the distance of 15 cm, the obtained efficiency evaluated via (5) is $\eta = 3.33\%$.

B. SAR Evaluation

After WPT evaluation, compliance with power absorption limits of body of patients undergoing endoscopy must also be checked. The power dissipated in the patient’s body by the Joule effect for non-ionizing radiation is regulated by the International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) [28]. Limits are set to 0.4 W/kg for the whole-body average SAR and 10 W/kg for the local head/torso SAR, within the range 100 kHz ÷ 300 GHz.

While the operating frequency of 6.78 MHz is an advantage for inductive link, the high frequency adversely affects eddy current losses in biological tissues. At first, we can consider the power dissipated in the patient’s body as mostly due to the action of TX coil. Under this assumption, a 3-D simulation was performed by using COMSOL Multiphysics[®] and by evaluating losses into a human mannequin caused by TX coil. For simplicity, the latter was schematized as a uniform current density contained in the hollow cylinder formed by the envelope of 6 windings. The current on the primary side was set to $I_{TX} = 3.8$ A from the results in Fig 5. The dielectric properties of human body tissues in the frequency range from 10 Hz to 100 GHz can be found in [29], and we extracted those at $f_0 = 6.78$ MHz (Table II, [30], [31]). Since the simulated body consists of a single solid, tissue properties were averaged according to their average percent weight in human body. Weight percentages do not sum up to 100% since some contributions to human weight were neglected.

Fig. 6 reports a 3-D view of the volumetric loss density iso-surfaces for three different positions of the TX coil along the body: chest, abdomen, and underbelly. The area interested by the losses is visible in the color scale, while the results are

TABLE II
ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF HUMAN ORGANS AT 6.78 MHz [29] AND THEIR WEIGHT AS A PERCENTAGE [30], [31].

Tissue name	Conductivity [S/m]	Relative permittivity	Reference Man ICRP 23 Organ percentage mass [%]
Blood	1.07	422.00	7.43
Bone Cancellous	0.12	89.90	2.86
Bone Marrow	0.01	23.50	4.29
Cartilage	0.35	253.00	1.57
Duodenum	0.76	359.00	0.53
Fat	0.03	16.30	19.29
Heart	0.47	389.00	0.47
Kidney	0.47	501.00	0.44
Liver	0.29	297.00	2.57
Lung Inflated	0.21	176.00	1.46
Muscle	0.60	233.00	40.00
Nerve	0.21	208.00	0.43
Pancreas	0.71	223.00	0.14
Skin Dry	0.15	478.00	3.71
Small Intestine	1.29	737.00	0.91
Spleen	0.45	634.00	0.26
Stomach	0.76	359.00	0.21

TABLE III
SAR VALUES FOR SIMULATIONS IN FIG. 6.

Position	P_B [W]	Total SAR [W/kg]	$\max\{P_B\}$ [W/m ³]	Localized SAR [W/kg]
Chest	9.60	0.113	7634.1	7.56
Abdomen	14.35	0.169	8765.3	8.42
Underbelly	13.78	0.162	8868.0	8.52

resumed in Table III. The TX coil was placed at 3 cm distance from skin. Given the power dissipated in the body P_B , the SAR on the total body can be evaluated by dividing P_B by the body mass (m_B). By considering an adult man with $m_B = 85$ kg, we obtained the highest value of $SAR = 0.141$ W/kg in the central position, i.e. the abdomen, still within the limit of 0.4 W/kg set by the ICNIRP. Precautionary, by assuming the highest value of body losses in W/m³ as the average on the most exposed 10-g cubic mass over 6-minutes time interval, results indicate a localized SAR value around 8 W/kg, compared to the limit of 10 W/kg (Table III). In first analysis, the WPT system designed and exercised turns out to be in accordance with power transfer specifications and compatible with absorption limits of the human body. The obtained localized SAR value suggests the possibility to use even more TX coils while remaining within the absorption limits but increasing the transferred power, for example with a Helmholtz coil-like structure.

C. Coil Prototypes

To validate the WPT system, electrical characteristics of the TX and RX coils and their mutual inductance have to be measured by varying the relative position. A first prototype of the 3-D RX coil is depicted in Fig. 7 (a). Each of the three coils with squared section of 1-cm side is realized with a wire of 0.05 mm diameter and connected to a single connection. The TX-coil prototype is actually under development and results of the experimental characterization of the WPT system will be presented at the conference.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the Wireless Power Transfer system developed within the AUTOCAPSULE Project for an autonomous multimodal implantable endoscopic capsule. In particular, the inductive link between the transmitting and the receiving coils was described with reference to the main involved parameters of the equivalent circuit model. Then, the simulated design of transmitting and receiving coils was presented by taking into account the power transferred to the load and the design constraints on available space and tissue absorption. The WPT system parameters were selected in such a way to satisfy a power transfer

Fig. 6. Power dissipated in the body (volumetric loss density iso-surface, W/m^3) in the 3-D SAR simulation for the TX coil placed in different positions along the body: (a) chest, (b) abdomen, and (c) underbelly.

Fig. 7. Prototype of the 3-D receiving coil.

of 150 mW to the end-user at a distance up to 15 cm, by showing compliance with SAR regulations. The experimental characterization of the WPT system is actually undergoing and measurement result will be shown at the conference.

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